

SELECTION OF THE COMPONENT BASE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE
CIRCUIT OF THE BROADCASTING TRANSMITTER

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Annotation: *AM transmitters are used for telephone communications, radio broadcasting, and transmission of television images. AM transmitters are used in all radio frequency ranges. The method of obtaining amplitude modulation depends on the purpose, power, energy and quality characteristics of the transmitter. In this regard, the article is devoted to the selection of the element base for the development of a broadcast transmitter circuit.*

Amplitude modulation can be carried out in any of the amplifying stages of the transmitter, if, according to the law of the information signal, the modulation factor is changed. The energy and quality indicators of the transmitter depend on which of the supply voltages is changed during modulation. There are two main types of simple modulation: by biasing the EC along the input circuit of the active element and by the supply voltage of the collector circuit E_p (collector modulation). Combined modulation is used, in which several supply voltages change simultaneously.

Shift modulation transmitters have a low efficiency, which prevents their use in broadcasting, professional communication systems. Such modulation is used in television, in the image channel, where the video signal has a wide bandwidth (up to 6 MHz). Such a signal is easier to obtain in the low power modulator inherent in offset modulation. In this case, the transmitter efficiency is low. The desired modulation quality with the highest possible efficiency is obtained with combined modulation, although this requires a more complex and powerful modulator.

The given useful (nominal) power is one of the main criteria that apply to transmitters. It is provided by the output (terminal) stage of the transmitter. The choice of an active element, especially transistors, to obtain a given transmitter power is a difficult task, since transistors have a small allowable power (see Table 1.1) and their parameters are highly frequency dependent.

The maximum power of one transistor in the range of long, medium and short waves reaches 250 W, meter 100 ... 125 W, decimeter - tens of watts; as the wavelength decreases further, the power decreases rapidly []. Consequently, it is possible to obtain a given transmitter power using transistors using the same methods as with radio tubes, only at low powers. It is appropriate to note here that due to the large spread of

parameters, transistors, when connected in parallel or in series in one stage, provide noticeably less useful power than the sum of the nominal powers of the used transistors.

Table 1.1.

Wave range, m	Transmitter power, kW				
	0,1...0,3	0,3...1	1...5	5...20	
0	100...1000	0,65...0,7	0,7...0,75	0,75...0,8	0,8...0,85
	10...100	0,6...0,65	0,65...0,7	0,7...0,75	0,75...0,8
	1...10	0,55...0,6	0,6...0,65	0,75...0,8	0,8...0,85

It is possible to turn on only two transistors in parallel or four in a push-pull circuit, two in a “shoulder”, but at the same time it is often necessary to introduce special resistors into the emitter circuit of each transistor to equalize their modes, which leads to a decrease in the power gain of the cascade.

A significant output power of transmitters (for example, more than 300 ... 500 W in the shortwave range) is obtained using bridge circuits for adding the power of several identical cascades (“modules”) [].

The construction of the transmitter according to this method somewhat increases its reliability, since the failure of one module, for example, the output stage, leads only to a certain decrease in power, but not to a complete loss of transmitter performance [].

Between the output terminal of the transmitter (the input of the antenna-feeder system) and the transistors of the output stage, there are always circuits for matching, filtering, etc. []. Despite the fact that they are usually performed on reactive elements (capacitors, inductors, transformers), some energy is always lost in them. At the initial stage of designing, nothing is known about these filtering and matching circuits, so it is necessary to take into account their properties approximately, based on the generalized parameters of the existing transmitters [].

Losses in the output filtering (oscillatory) system of the transmitter in the first approximation can be taken into account by taking the approximate values of the efficiency of the output filtering system (η_{OFS}) from [] tab. 1.1.

Smaller efficiency values refer to the output filtering systems consisting of 1...2 circuits, larger ones - from 3...4 circuits. The increase in the efficiency of the output filtering systems as the number of circuits increases is due to the ability to strengthen the connection between them without fear that the filtering will be lower than required; the strengthening of the connection leads to an increase in the insertion resistance R_{IN} and, consequently, the efficiency of the output filtering system:

$$\eta_{OFS} = \frac{\mathcal{R}B}{(r_k + \mathcal{R}_{IN})}, \text{ where is } r_k \text{ — loop loss resistance.}$$

When building amplification stages based on broadband transformers, one should take into account the efficiency of the output transformer of the output stage $\eta_{TR} \approx 0.85...0.95$.

Power addition and distribution devices have an efficiency factor $\eta_{ADD} \approx 0.8...0.9$. Thus, the required (nominal) power of the transistors of the output stage of the transmitter is greater than the specified output power:

$$P_{nom} \geq \frac{Pa}{(\eta_{OFS} \cdot \eta_{Tr} \cdot \eta_{Add})}$$

Here it is appropriate to recall that with amplitude and single-sideband modulation, the choice of transistors is carried out at maximum power.

Comparison of the required power of the output stage with the unit power of transistors in a given frequency range makes it possible to make a decision on the possibility of obtaining the required power from one (output) stage with a number of transistors not more than four or on the need to apply a system for adding the power of several modules. When building a transmitter, to simplify its tuning, the modules are built as broadband amplifiers []. In order to increase the efficiency, a transistor mode with a current cutoff, as well as a key one, is used. When operating with current cutoff, a push-pull circuit and cutoff angle $\theta = 90^\circ$ are used to provide an approximately harmonic voltage shape at the output of the broadband module [].

The number of modules in the output stage of the transmitter depends on the specified transmitter power and the power of one module, which, in turn, is determined by the power of the transistors and their number in the module (usually 2 or 4).

When choosing transistors for an output stage (or module), it is necessary to compare several types of transistors that provide a given power. To do this, you can use the table (see, for example, Table 2), from which the type of transistor is finally selected, which best meets all the requirements for the transmitter [].

Transistor selection criterion: suitability for use in new developments; expedient from the point of view of the complete structural diagram of the transmitter, the standard supply voltage of the cascade E_k ; suitability for amplifying single-sideband signals at a given power and acceptable distortion; if possible, high values of the power gain K_p and the efficiency of the collector circuit η ; low cost of a set of transistors.

Reference books [], allow, as a first approximation, to identify transistors suitable for comparison and their required number m in the cascade (Table 2).

Table 2.

De vice	Limit parameters									
	at T = 25°C									
	K_{max}, A	$K_{и, max}, A$	$U_{KЕ0}, V$	$U_{K, max}, B$	U_{max}, B	U_{KB}, V	U_{EB0}, V	$U_{K, max}, W_t$	$T_K, °C$	$T_{п, max}, °C$

KT 602 A	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	20	1 5	8
KT 602 Б	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	20	1 5	8
KT 602 B	(,075	(,5		70	8	80	5 ,8	25	20	1 5	8
KT 602 Г	(,075	(,5		70	8	80	5 ,8	25	20	1 5	8
KT 602 AM	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	20	1 5	8
KT 602 BM	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	20	1 5	8
2T 602 A	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	50	1 25	1
2T 602 Б	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	50	1 25	1
2T 602 AM	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	50	1 25	1
2T 602 BM	(,075	(,5	(0)	(7 2	1 2	120	5 ,8	25	50	1 25	1

As follows from Table. 2, the initial data corresponds to the transistor KT602. Requirements for power and distortion are maintained with a small margin.

Transmitters are usually required to have high frequency stability [1]. The specified frequency stability can be achieved using automatic frequency control.

However, most often the stability of the oscillator is ensured by using quartz stabilization [2]. Since self-oscillators have a small output power, therefore, modern transmitters are built according to a multi-stage block diagram. At present, typical frequency exciters based on frequency synthesizers have been developed. Recommendations for the selection and use of pathogens are given in [3]. There is also a list of typical exciters produced by the industry and their main parameters.

When considering drawing up a circuit, you can do without ready-made exciters and use self-oscillators with quartz to obtain a given high stability.

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